

Resilient Hosting of Research Data Management Services

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ABSTRACT

Modern research relies on digital data services [1]. As an infrastructure provider, it is crucial to offer a reliable and resilient environment. Users of research data tools expect uninterrupted access to web-based platforms and protection from data loss or downtime. Limited availability causes research delays, collaboration issues, user dissatisfaction, and abandonment of resources. Such expectation can be met by high availability (HA) environments for services such as data analysis tools, data management resources (i.e., GitLab as DataHUB [2], [3]), and even chat tools like Element. While improving service quality, the presented approach reduces manual intervention through automation.

Objectives: The primary objectives of an HA environment are to minimize downtime in the event of a failure, prevent data loss, and facilitate automatic failover to ensure service stability. Another goal is to establish a flexible, cost-effective HA environment that avoids technology and vendor lock-in. Consequently, the presented approach relies on open-source components and a cluster of virtual machines (VMs). Unlike generic HA deployments, our setup is customized for research data infrastructures and scientific gateways, with lightweight resource requirements and configurations tailored for service continuity in research environments.

Core Components: The key components are Pacemaker [4] and Distributed Replicated Block Devices (DRBD) [5]. DRBD uses real-time data replication, ensuring copies of the main server are available on backup servers. Pacemaker manages the cluster, establishing an active primary node and passive secondary nodes. Upon any cluster issues, it automatically fails over by switching the primary. A key feature is Pacemaker's fencing mechanism, preventing multiple servers from writing concurrently to same data, thereby minimizing corruption and ensuring integrity. Combined with DRBD, this allows immediate takeover by another server to maintain access to applications and data. Corosync [6] is used alongside Pacemaker as a communication layer, enabling reliable messaging and quorum handling, ensuring all nodes are aware of each other for coordinated failover and cluster stability.

Use Case: To demonstrate a real-world scenario using this HA setup, we implemented GitLab as a core data management service within the DataPLANT consortium. Hosted on a two-node cluster with DRBD-backed storage and Pacemaker orchestration, GitLab operates with automated failover and fencing enabled. This ensures that researchers have uninterrupted access to critical services like data versioning and other research workflows. As a concrete user-facing example, the GitLab service remains fully operational during node failure or maintenance, improving user experience and supporting collaboration without disruptions.

Scalability: Scalability is a key advantage of this setup. As research projects grow, the system can scale by adding servers or adjusting configurations. This HA setup offers the stability and reliability needed to support more users, larger datasets, and increasingly complex research workflows.

Conclusion: Combining Pacemaker and DRBD provides a reliable high-availability solution for hosting applications like GitLab for research data management. Data is continuously replicated and protected by fencing mechanisms to guarantee availability and prevent loss or corruption, thereby supporting seamless research workflows. This approach directly improves user experience by reducing service interruptions. The increased resilience of scientific gateways leads to higher user acceptance and satisfaction.

Keywords—High availability, research data management, Pacemaker, DRBD, GitLab, failover, science gateways

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